

ISSUES INFLUENCING LEARNING OF STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS IN TANZANIA VOCATIONAL TRAINING CENTRES

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Abstract:

The study investigated issues which influence learning of Students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in inclusive Dar es Salaam Vocational Training Centers (VTCs). Qualitative and quantitative research approaches as well as survey research design were employed. Interviews, observations and documentary review were data collection methods used to collect data both primary and secondary data. Analysis of data was done based on research objectives; Findings indicated scarcity of instructional and learning of facilities/equipment in VTC. Despite, inadequacy of training facilities in some students with SEN were reported to use facilities/equipment designed for learners without SEN and this negatively affected learning. The learning environment for learners with SEN was unfriendly coupled with an unsuitable teaching methodology despite of employment of mixed instructional methods. The results conclude that, inclusive education is implemented in VTCs, and that students with SEN are capable of learning vocational skills on condition that they are provided with special training/learning facilities/equipment and conducive environments. Recommendations include: VTCs management to ensure availability of instruction and learning facilities in VTCs and instructors to use of variety of instructional methods.

Keywords: vocational skills, special educational needs and vocational training centres

1. Introduction

In today's economy, jobs that involve the employment of vocational skills are increasingly becoming important. This is why Vocational Education and Training (VET) programmes are popular in Tanzania and important to all types of people including the physically handicapped (the focus of this study). VET provides careers based upon manual or practical fields. Because of this orientation of vocational training, learners with special educational needs, require educational support to cater for their special

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educational needs to enable them acquire vocational skills in inclusive settings. Vocational training has an on-the-job training component. The provision of VET opportunities to students SEN is supported by economic reasons. First, on completion of their studies, VTCs graduates gain either self or wage employment or both. In light of this, the provision of skill training for students with SEN is beneficial to society since graduates are explained to effectively engage into socio-economic activities.

However, the barriers to such training of students with SEN include attitudinal and physical obstacles which generally prevent effective participation of students with SEN in learning vocational skills in Tanzania's VTCs and workplace. The investigation on the current situation with regard to the extent students with SEN learns vocational skills in inclusive VTCs entails to cover the existing gap. These prejudices make individuals SEN to be treated as burdens to the nation and considered incapable of contributing to the development of society (Georges, 2004). Historically, In Tanzania VET has existed prior to the colonial era and training was largely informal. People with physical disabilities were generally hidden in homes by parents and relatives because the impairment was believed to be a punishment from God or a curse in the family (Athuman, 1998). As a result, people with disabilities were '*denied*' the opportunity to participate in vocational training: they were also denied the opportunity to gain wage or self-employment or both.

Over the years, notable and gradual changes have opened no opportunities for such disadvantaged members of society to benefit from vocational training leaving other group of people (those without special education needs) enjoying the outcomes of learning vocational skills. However, during the colonial period, VET was made formal and learners with special educational needs were provided with VET under segregated environment through was called '*special education*'. VTCs and trade schools such as Buigiri for the visually impaired as well as Yombo VTCs for the physically handicapped, were specifically built for training such members of the society. The practice of separating students with SEN generally excluded them from complete socialization with other students.

In the post-independence period, global radical changes in the education provision demanded that all learners be integrated in learning under '*inclusion*' policy. Both students with and without SEN were to be brought together in the same class/workshop (Whitaker, 1998). The inclusion of all special educational needs learners in the regular classroom is independent of the nature and severity of their SEN (Lefrancois, 1997). Tanzania introduced inclusive education in VTCs to enable all interested learners to get knowledge and skills essential for wage and self-employment. The introduction of inclusive education in VTC was in line with the VET Act of 1994, which aimed at providing Vocational Training (VET) to disadvantaged groups of people such as women and the handicapped. However, there is no clear and specific vocational policy on students with SEN.

2. Problem Statement and Research Objectives

Inclusive education in Tanzania's Vocational Education and Training System (VETS) has been devised as a strategy to ensure effective skill learning of all types of learners in the VTCs. The main objective was to bridge the gap which existed in VTCs whereby by the majority of students with SEN had no opportunity to access it. Despite the objective, the outcomes of training in inclusive settings have been problematic, specifically on the side of learners with SEN. In 2010, for example, only 24.2% of students with SEN passed basic course examinations. In 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015, examination passes were 32.9%, 26.6%, 38.2% and 26.5%, respectively. The results were lower compared to their counter parts (students without SEN) whose average pass in the same period was 80.4%. Also, the average drop-outs rate for learners with special educational needs in VTCs for years 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015 accounted for 19.3% annually compared to only 7% for learners without special needs (VETA, 2016).

Furthermore, the issues of how students with SEN learn vocational skills in '*inclusive*' classrooms and workshops in different subjects in VTCs as well as the determination of their skill competencies have not been given much concern in Tanzania due to the absence of an empirical legal framework on inclusive education in the VET system. In fact, only 15% public VTCs in Tanzania are implementing inclusive education at the time when this study was being conducted. What remained unexplored was the extent to which learners with special educational needs effectively learn vocational skills in Tanzania's VTCs, which is the basis of this study. The main objective of the study was to investigate issues which influence learning of vocational skills among students with SEN in inclusive VTCs. Specifically, the study: (i) Determined the availability of instructional/learning facilities in VTCs and (ii) Assessed instructional/learning environments for Students with SEN (ii) Instructional and learning environments (iii) Analyzed instructional and learning methodologies for students with SEN.

2. Theoretical and Empirical Literature

2.1 Theory which Guided the Study

The Social Cognition Learning theory was employed in the study. It highlights the fact that culture in the prevailing environments is the prime determinant of individual development. A core principle of the Social Cognition Learning theory is that culture makes two types of contributions to a child's intellectual development. Under this theory, students acquire much of their knowledge and skills through their culture which provides them with the processes or means of their thinking and performance of a number of tasks. The theory disputes the cultural belief to the effect that students with SEN are incapable of learning and performing skills. In brief, this theory, upholds that culture teaches learners in general what to think, how to think and how to do things (skills)

Under this theory, cognitive development results from a dialectical process that allows a child to learn through problem-solving experiences shared with someone else, usually a parent or teacher, a sibling or peer, to learn. The person interacting with the child initially assumes most of the responsibility for guiding the problem-solving, but gradually this responsibility is transferred to the child (Bogner, 2004). Since much of what children learn from the environment (outside schooling) comes from the culture around them, and that much of the child's problem solving is mediated through an adult's help, it is wrong to focus on child isolation (Bogner, 2004). Thus, the focus during teaching should be on all learners in a class. In this regard, instructors should use multiple numbers of teaching methods. This theory was adopted in this study because of its impact on development of children outside the schools in the environment

2.2 The Concept of Vocational Skill and Skill Learning

Vocational skill being a concept is a challenge to researchers. Barrow (2008) explains that researchers have been using widely varying conceptions of skills which resulted in inconsistent and contradictory findings. Barrow (ibid) observes that critical thinking cannot be described as a skill because it both requires both a set of skills and because its application in a context. Nevertheless, critical thinking is connected in some way with certain features of mind and perhaps even constituted by certain attributes of mind is cogently persuasive. Barrow (ibid) is also critical of bundling all sorts of human activity under the general term of skills. Instead, he makes such skills major distinctions physical, motor, intellectual, interpersonal, perceptual skills and creative skills. At first sight, the development of creative skills is different from the development of motor skills. However, one could be creative at the same time acquire some motor skills.

Thus, even creative skills may be qualitatively different and acquired differently in different domains of human conduct. Barrow (ibid) suggests that some skills require intellectual dimensions, which are partly physical and partly intellectual. The way a skill is taught is dependent on how instructors interpret the needs of their learners to shape the subject content in ways which make it accessible to learners with different learning needs as well as different levels and kinds of knowledge. Generally, there are no skills, competencies, or capabilities which do not have a *cognitive* or intellectual component which influences the level of expertise of skillfulness of performance, or the acquisition and development of skills. In fact, lack of motivation, or a lack of maturity, can influence a person's ability to acquire skills.

2.3 Nature and Causes of SEN

Donald (1993) defines learners SEN as learners with physical, sensory, intellectual, emotional, and social or any combination of these and other aspects which affect their learning capacity in formal education educational institutions. It is generally acknowledged that physical, intellectual and emotional handicaps necessitate the provision of education to people with facilities and equipment to victims during

learning, which are different from those used by normal students. In general terms, such learners are called 'students with special educational needs'.

Statistics in South Africa for the year 2012 suggest that 21.4% to 25% of the population live in poverty and is believed that poor people are more disposed to health risks associated with malnutrition, diseases and infection. The Department of Health (2000) stipulates that many health risks are in line with poverty which results also in cognitive and sensory impairments that affect people morphologically as well as mentally. The situation causes them to be in a group of people with special needs during learning (Kanyikle, 2013).

People with special needs generally face various challenges in the community. The most common challenges have been observed at household level. Weichers (1999) maintains that some parents/guardians are passive when it comes to children with special needs; they lack interest and are generally ignorant about the value of the inputs for children with special needs in educational institutions and at home.

2.4 Inclusion in a Global Perspective

There is no clear stipulation with regard to the impetus of inclusion because explanations on how inclusion came about into existence differ from one country to another. Back in the 1960s, children with special needs were seen as a problem in society; they were excluded from the mainstream educational system (Spetch, 2003). The policy of exclusion began to pave way for inclusion as early intervention theories were developed. These theories supported the idea that the sooner children received special education the better their development and ability to progress become. In United States, Education for All Handicapped Children Act of 1975 required all public schools in that country to provide services for children with diagnosed special needs.

The Act also stipulated that all children be educated in the 'least restrictive environment'. Out of that law, was introduced the idea of mainstreaming, which means pulling a child out of special education classrooms and putting him or her in a regular classroom. Spetch (2003) explains that mainstreaming was not cost-effective, and needed bigger percentage of academic budget seemed to support it. The concept of inclusion followed mainstreaming. According to the author, inclusion is a difficult word to define and Inclusion varies from programme to another. Strictly speaking, inclusion differs from mainstreaming because it eliminates pull-outs and self-contained classrooms.

Before the Salamanca Statement, people with special needs were not given special concern in the education system. They were considered the last to be offered access to education, and they were neglected and nobody even themselves would think that they would participate in building of their nations. They were considered inferior and needed special attention from their families. Like gender opportunity, inclusion in education is currently a global agenda also supporting the Human rights perspective as it is stated in a statement "*inclusion and participation are essential to human dignity and the*

enjoyment and exercise of human rights” (Balescut and Eklindh, 2003). The Jomtien World Conference on Education for All (EFA) in 1990 paved a way for inclusion.

The Jomtien conference decided to remove exclusion from the educational system and explaining that learning needs for people with special needs demand special attention. Therefore, steps need to be taken to provide equal access to education to every category of persons with special needs as an integral part of the education system (Balescut and Eklindh, 2003). In fact, the UNESCO Salamanca statement (1994) calls on the international community to endorse the of inclusive approach education institutions by implementing philosophical and strategic changes. A total of 92 governments and 25 international organizations agreed to a dynamic new statement in 1994 stipulating on inclusive education the norm. Towards this direction, the Framework for Action as a guiding principle uses education institution, including VTCs to enroll all people regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions.

2.5 Benefits of Inclusion in Educational Institutions

Benefits of Inclusion have been categorized in four aspects:

A. Inclusion Improves Learning

When trainees with special educational needs are mixed with those without special educational needs, both groups is motivated to learn effectively. Under such circumstances, instructors opt to break instructions into finer parts or repeat directions if they have a child in the class with deafness, blindness, or a developmental disability. Doing so instructors enables both groups of learners to acquire skills in the subject matter because everyone is provided with learning facilities to cope with his/her learning needs. In carpentry and joinery trade, learners are given saws which help them cope with their special educational needs.

Breaking instructions into small parts enables learners to correctly perform all tasks in carpentry and joinery trades. The same is applicable for visually impaired learners who are provided with Braille materials, typewriters and tape recorders for writing and listening instructions. Similarly, division of instructions into small parts simplifies learning for learners without special needs. This enables them to easily grasp concepts in the theoretical part and acquire skills during practical sections.

B. Training Learners to Accept their Colleagues with Individual Differences

The best way to help trainees overcome their misconceptions about their fellows with special needs is to bring them together in integrated settings. Education institutions have been identified as settings that can diverse groups to value one another. Although inclusive education is in practice in Tanzania’s VTCs, the 1994 VET Policy about learners with special educational needs fail to clearly spell out the benefits for such learners. As a result, the inclusion policy for learners with SEN has only been limited effect.

C. Trainees Developing New Friendships

Trainees with special needs who are included in regular classrooms develop friendship and benefits from peer interaction in their communities. Visibility and socialization helps them participate in different socio-economic activities. In the VTCs for example, learners with special needs gain competencies while learning skills because of social interaction with instructors and fellow learners. The competencies gained in turn make them eligible for wage or self-employment in the formal or informal sectors of production or services.

D. Minimizing Parents' Negative Attitudes towards Children's Lives and Education are Removed

Society members' negative attitudes towards people with special needs can be mitigated through the provision of inclusive education. When trainees with special needs are integrated into local education institutions, parents have more opportunities to participate in schools and communities where these schools are located. As a result, negative attitudes towards their children start to ebb away because societies value their children. Indeed, in recent years, inclusive education has been motivating parents to enroll their children in education institutions rather than hide them at home. To some extent, inclusive education has increased learners opportunities in life because they are provided with essential basic facilities in their lives.

E. Legal Rights

Trainees with special needs have a legal right to attend regular classes and receive an appropriate education in the least restrictive environment. Benefits of inclusion include quality instructional time with peers without special educational needs which help learners with special actual strategies taught by instructors. Instructors bring in different ways to instruct a lesson for special needs learners and peers without need. Thus, universally, apart from various statutes, declarations, there are legal frameworks being instituted to safeguard the rights of learners with SEN so that against.

3. Historical Background of Special Needs Education (SNE) in Tanzania

3.1 Early Institutions and Process

Special needs education in Tanzania was historically developed and supported by non-governmental organisations. The first education services in Tanzania were made up of residential special schools built by religious organisations. The first school for the visually impaired people was established in 1950 by the Anglican Church at Buigiri in Dodoma. The Roman Catholic Church opened the first school for deaf children in 1963. Also, services for persons with physical disabilities were founded by the Salvation Army in 1967 at Mgulani in Dar es Salaam.

The historical development of special needs education in Tanzania follows the development in many other countries. Services for certain disability groups (the blind and the deaf) provided by churches and charity organizations followed by small-scale educational provisions in special schools for other disability groups (e.g. persons with

physical and intellectual disabilities). On the whole, more government intervention and support services in public schools are necessary to make inclusive education facilities universally accessible to Tanzania's learners with SEN.

3.2 Special Educational Needs (SEN) Teacher Training in Tanzania

The government of Tanzania generally advocates that all schools should provide education to learners with disabilities and other barriers to learning. One of the constraints for achieving Education for All is the lack of knowledge in the field of special education. Only 0.9 percent of the teaching force out of over 118,000 teachers, have special needs education teacher training (MoEVT, 2009). Patandi Teachers' College (PTC) was only one College for teaching special educational needs teachers in Tanzania, currently there are other educational training institutions such as University of Dodoma and Sebastian Koloa University College (SEKUCO), the latter being the newly established higher education institution that offers degree courses in special educational needs.

The Patandi College started to train such specialist teachers in 1996, when the Government of Tanzania decided to move such training from Tabora Teacher's College to Patandi. The college offers courses for grade 'A' teachers in mainstream education and special needs education teachers at Certificate level which is a one year course. It offers a two year Diploma course in Special Needs Education. The specializations certificate and diploma levels are for visual, hearing and intellectual Impairments. From 1996 to 2004, the total number of students who have completed their special needs education teacher training is 821 teachers, 682 at the certificate and 139 at diploma level (MoEVT, 2009).

Subjects taught in the special needs education courses at both certificate and diploma levels differ from one course to another, depending on the specialization. The subjects which are common to all students in special needs education are aimed at *"equipping students-teachers with basic concepts and skills of all fields of impairments which are offered at the College"*. The common subjects include teaching methodology and techniques, assessment techniques, educational psychology, philosophy of education, guidance and counseling and intervention procedures. Areas focusing on specific disabilities comprise autism, deaf, blindness, learning disabilities, emotional and behavioural disorders, speech and language disorders, physical disabilities. Health related conditions and that severe and multiple disabilities are not catered for.

In fact, the concept of Inclusive Education was not one of the subjects taught. On the whole, Patandi TC offers specialized knowledge only on three disability areas but there is also a great need for generalist knowledge in all disability areas for every special needs education teacher (MoEVT, 2007). It is evident that there is no institution in Tanzania that provides adequate special education needs teacher training for teaching in inclusive VTCs. Furthermore, the Morogoro Vocational Teachers Training College (MVTTC) curriculum is silent on methodologies for teaching learners with special educational needs in Tanzania inclusive VTCs. And yet PEDP (2007) directs that

the Tanzania Local Government Authorities should be charged with the responsibility of ensuring that persons with disability or special educational needs receive adequate education and support services in their own community or as close to home as possible.

The fact-finding team recognizes the paramount importance of vocational and life skills for improving the employment opportunities of disabled learners, who complete or drop out of school. Moreover, Vocational and life skills should be included in primary and secondary education whenever possible. Above all, non-formal and vocational education and training, should also increasingly take into account the needs of disabled learners.

3.3 Empirical Literature

Banerji and Dailey (1995) conducted a study on *Effectiveness of inclusive outcomes*. A specific focus was on students with educational needs. It was revealed from the study that learners with specific learning disabilities demonstrated academic progress at a pace comparable to that of students without such disabilities. The study also revealed that teachers and parents indicated progress in self-esteem and motivation.

Vaughn, Elbaum and Schumm (2006), in their study conducted in elementary school in California about social function, learners with learning disabilities in an inclusive classroom were assessed in-terms of peer acceptance, loneliness, self-concept and social alienation. The researchers found that such learners demonstrated lower academic self-concept.

Stanovich et al (1998) conducted a study about differences in academic self-concept and peer acceptance in an inclusive classroom setting. The findings showed that self-concept was lowest among the categorized students than none categorized ones. Another study by Klingner *et al* (1998) was conducted to find out the models preferred by students (pull-out or inclusion). The results indicated that more children preferred the pull-out model than others. Praisner (2003) surveyed 408 elementary schools in USA to determine principal's attitudes towards inclusion. The study found that one out of five principals' attitudes was positive, when the variable of special education concepts had been taken into account. Wang and Walberg (2001) surveyed the experts in instruction and learning to develop a conceptual framework in inclusive settings.

A study conducted by Mutarubukwa (2006) on the performance of trainees and VTCs revealed that lack of qualified and competent instructors, lack of facilities as well as under utilization of available resources and non-conducive environment impinged negative effects to learners' performances in trade tests and VTCs. An empirical survey conducted by VETA (1996) in Tanzania on employment and employability of graduates with special needs indicated that only 13.3 percent were in gainful employment in the formal sector and 43.1 percent were self-employed.

4. Methodology of the Study

The study was done in VTCs located Dar es Salaam region and 260 respondents participated. Both qualitative and quantitative research approaches were used. Survey research design was employed and data was collected through the use of data collection methods such as interviews, observations and documentary review. Analysis of data was based on researcher objectives.

4.1 Research Outcomes, Conclusion and Recommendations

A. Availability of Instructional and Learning Facilities in VTCs

It was revealed from the study that VTCs in Dar es Salaam region, showed a shortage of 35% of tailoring sewing machines. The sewing machines available were 520 less than the required by 800 learners. At least 78.8% of the required machines were available for learners without special educational needs out of which 290 (70%) were functioning. For learners with special educational needs who needed more time to learn various skills, there were only 39% special sewing machines for 61% users. Further investigations, specifically on the facilities and equipment in the tailoring and Carpentry and Joinery (CJ) subjects, revealed that the VTCs under study had a total of 1,377 of facilities such as buildings, classrooms, and workshops for those Trades. However, the number of facilities in actual use were only 750 (35.7%) of the total number that is required by all VTCs in Dar es Salaam region.

It was also observed that teaching/learning facilities available in VTCs were 3662 and facilities in use were 1896 (33.97%) out of the total 5580 (100%) sewing machines required for the tailoring trade. On the whole, privately owned institutions had a fewer facilities due to the lack of sufficient funds to meet costs. Five (1.8%) of the respondents in private VTCs had fewer sources of funds than in public institutions. AS a result, their ability to buy adequate training and learning facilities was low. The observations at one private VTC revealed that 65% of the facilities in Tailoring Trade were for learners without special educational needs and the remaining 35 percent tailoring trade facilities were for learners with special educational needs.

Conclusively, the analysis of the scarcity of instructional and learning facilities in the VTCs revealed that student with special educational needs were negatively affected by such shortages. The situation has resulted to failure of many of them in executing practical attributes during skill learning as well as in the final examinations trade tests. Failure conducting practical attributes during learning affected the effective grasping of different operations within a task. As a result, the students with special educational needs were also unable to integrate the theory learned in classrooms into practical in the workshops.

B. Instructional/Learning Environments for Students with SEN

The study initially sought to establish attitudinal measures by asking respondents the extent to which they perceived/viewed learning environments specifically for students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in VTCs. Findings indicate that 40 (14%)

respondents from a group of students with special educational needs said that instructional and learning environment were *'bad'*. However, the analysis of their responses indicated that their responses related to 10(3.6%) respondents who said that instructional and learning environment were *'very bad'*. In light of this, they claimed that their VTCs were situated in very poor environment which were not conducive for learning.

Findings also indicated that 60 respondents (21.7%) said that learning environments were *'very good'* and 40 respondents (14.5%) said that the environments were just good. They explained that the good buildings for theory and practical training and infrastructures such as toilets, dormitories, walking tracks and play grounds were just as good when compared to those available in other training institutions. It was reported that students with special educational needs learned knowledge and skills effectively.

With regard to objective measures, the researcher physically surveyed VTCs environments and noted that 45% of studied VTCs had infrastructures which were friendly to students with SEN. There were also toilets for them in dormitories and classrooms/workshops. There were passage ways constructed to be used by physically handicapped learners. It was reported that learners with special educational needs in VTCs with friendly environment learned tailoring and Carpentry/Joinery trades effectively (vice-versa).

Based on the fact that students with special educational needs require careful handling during learning (Whitaker, 1998) it is concluded that findings in the current study showed that external interruptions made many of them lose their classrooms/workshop attention and focused on the outside stimuli. The resultant loss of classrooms/workshops concentration was detrimental to their learning.

C. Instructional and Learning Methodologies for Learners with Special Educational Needs

It was revealed from the study that in 10 observations 45(26.6%) instructors extensively employed *'lecture'* method during instruction because it was argued to be the easiest method which every instructor especially those in new teaching profession can easily use since it involves talking and writing on the chalkboard. In light of this, two (5.1%) instructors said that lecture method was good especially for blind students who were able to listen to what instructors were talking in a class and hence, able to follow instructional process. It is contended from the study that the instructors' competencies in using the lecture method enabled students to learn theory part effectively by asking elaborations to the areas of the subject where they did not understand. Thus, instructors' competencies are important in facilitating trainees' learning because are the main actors in the learning environment (Jokolo, 2003). Despite this, in the Tailoring subject there were two deaf learners. In such situation respondent's response was not valid because the instruction method (lecture) did not meet learning needs (Watkins, 2007).

In two observations, 20(11.8%) instructors were observed using '*discussion*' method during instruction and in 25 observations, 30(17.7%) instructors were observed using '*demonstration*' during instructions. It was also revealed from the study that '*field study*' and '*simulation*' methods were occasionally used by instructors during instructions. It was revealed from the study that apart from use of lecture method, '*mixed instructional*' methods were popular. It was observed that instructors usually use lecture, demonstration and simulation methods to instruct students in inclusive settings. This was due to the contention that '*mixed instructional*' methods enabled students to learn effectively because all students' interests are covered during instruction. The researcher thought that the use of '*mixed instruction*' method was appropriate for effective learning of vocational skills since the instruction of vocational skill subjects is different from teaching arts subjects such as History, Kiswahili and French. While the former need adequate demonstrations and practical which lead to discovery, instruction of the latter do not demand much of the demonstration instead application of different teaching strategies. Instructor's use of mixed instructional methods enabled students to acquire vocational skills which also enabled them to undertake different operations in workshops.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, VET is important in the country's socio-economic development. It facilitates people to increase knowledge and skills essential for self and wage employment. Knowledge and skills are provided by VTCs through effective training hence this calls for availability of teaching-learning facilities and equipment in VTCs and quality training to enable graduates come up with competencies essential for executing diverse operations for given tasks in production and service sectors. It was realized that employability of VTCs graduates with SEN is related to skill acquired; therefore, skilled graduates get employed than unskilled one.

It is further concluded that instructional and learning methodologies are essential for effective vocational skill learning among student with SEN. However, using the lecture method in teaching practical vocational skills does not provide hands on experience to students. The lecture method was seldom used in technical and vocational teaching because it was not effective in teaching productive skill (Fryklund, 1970). Thus, the use of teaching aids and devices during in lectures motivated learners with special educational needs to learn vocational skills and that the use of written instructions added value to the use of teaching aids and devices. The following are recommendations: For instruction and learning facilities/equipment, VTCs managements should ensure enough availability of students with SEN facilities/equipment for effective vocational skill learning. For instructional/learning environments for students with SEN, the policy on SEN students to be formulated and this will stipulated the environments into which they will effectively learn skills. For

instructional and learning methodologies mixed instructional methods to be extensively employed in order to enable SEN students to learn effectively in inclusive setting.

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